

Toward a Feminist Organology: Moya Henderson, Sekko, and Genealogies of Resistance

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Abstract

This research proposes a feminist organology as a speculative framework for interrogating the epistemic, material, and relational conditions of instrumentality in Western art music. Drawing on feminist genealogy, historiography, and archival research, it traces Australian composer Moya Henderson's 1976 work *Sekko*, and her subsequent invention of the Alemba: a keyboard percussion instrument comprising three chromatic octaves of tuned triangles. Despite Henderson's pioneering and often controversial contributions to Australian contemporary music, her visionary approach to instrument design and its interface with percussion has been largely overlooked. Through engaging with feminist, post-humanist, and decolonial discourses, this research argues that Henderson's practices disrupt normative hierarchies and totalizing orthodoxies within percussion history, while also reflecting on how constructs of power occupy spaces and perpetuate privileges that sustain inequalities in cultural and creative practices. Furthermore, it examines how instruments operate as sites of gendered labour and resistance, exploring the potentials of feminist organology to invite new forms of expression, phenomenological understanding, and object-oriented ontologies.

Introduction

Originality was my first consideration, and experimentation is still a very strong requirement for my work. But now I see originality as a part of the creative process that flows from my overriding requirement of honesty ... Being true to yourself often means experimenting and going against accepted ways of writing music.

—Moya Henderson, quoted in Donald (1986, p. 62)

Australian scholar and composer Andrew Ford posits in *The Shortest History of Music* that “alongside any history of change there will always be continuity” (Ford 2024, p. 2). I take this insight as a frame for examining the tensions between continuity and progress in contemporary musical epistemologies and practices. Western art music is deeply entangled in the complex web of relations that bind power and knowledge. Its histories and practices are shaped by institutional economies, discursive norms, and the inherited canonical conditions that govern what can be imagined, enacted, and embraced in our present creative ecosystems. I argue that the aspects in which we are governed by, constitute the kinds of persons we take ourselves to be, and therefore, politics are a matter of the personal, and inseparable from life itself (Gutting 2005). Thus, there is no

clear line drawn between those on the side of power, and those on the side of resistance (Foucault 2003). Therefore, it is imperative to render visible other ways of thinking, acting, and co-constituting in the present. Acts that are in relation to our “pleasures, labours, troubles, hopes, aspirations”, and subsequently our freedoms (Foucault 2003, p. ix).

Michel Foucault’s notion of genealogy offers one such movement of thought, exploring how our present has taken shape through successive attempts at resolving historical resistances. Therefore, genealogy offers a mode of inquiry that neither seeks origins, nor inscribes linear histories. Instead, it critically traces the circuits linking knowledge and practices, mapping deviations within the apparatuses that govern bodies and actions (Foucault 2003).

Genealogical and archival work often begins in seemingly unpromising places. It demands a meticulous labour to locate and unsettle historical narratives, frequently with sites deemed peripheral: correspondence, notes, diaries, letters, institutional refusals etc. Scholar Sara Ahmed describes the fragile composition of such an archive as part of the work of living a feminist life, where feminism is a fragile archive of “shattering and splattering”: practical, yet messy, critical, and incomplete work, whose fragility imparts a responsibility “to take care” (Ahmed 2017, p. 17). These messy “crisscrossing, overlapping, and interconnected ways that one exists in life” (Thomas-Durrell 2023, p. 170) are crucial sites of knowledge for understanding how our present has taken shape (Mellor 1988). From this perspective, this work engages in tracing feminist genealogies: a speculative method that interrogates musical histories through their doings, reciprocities, and resistances (Lloyd-Jones 2024).

Naming a project speculative or attempting to trace histories signals a critical approach to reading the present. As Maria Puig de la Bellacasa asserts, speculative projects connect “to a feminist tradition” in which thinking about what is “possible” means enquoteprovoking political and ethical imagination in the present (Bellacasa 2017, p. 7). Therefore, this research does not offer a linear reading of history, or chronological biography, but rather it is concerned with a feminist genealogical reading of Australian composer and instrument inventor Moya Henderson’s 1976 work *Sekko: for its water*—a composition for solo percussionist and sculpture, consisting of twenty-seven triangle-like objects.

Rather than framing Henderson’s innovations as pragmatic progressions, this research argues that Henderson’s instrument design and compositions emerge through resistances to the apparatuses of Western art music: the implicit and explicit network of rules that regulate composition, instrument design, and performance practice. Through this line of inquiry, *Sekko* becomes a theatre of procedures: a work that exposes, reconfigures, and disrupts historical norms, through situated knowledges and co-constituted entanglements (Foucault 2003; Barad 2007; Haraway 1988). From this conceptual ground, I tentatively propose a feminist organology—a critical orientation and conceptual framework for thinking through Henderson’s work. *Sekko*, together with her subsequent invention of the keyboard percussion instrument, the Alemba, opens movements of thought that trace the fault lines of the organological conditions in the present. Hen-

derson's instruments can be read as sites of gendered labour that critique institutional economies and foreground embodied techniques of making through acts of feminist inquiry. Thus, Henderson's oeuvre offers a compelling case for this conceptual move. Feminist work does not always offer solutions, but rather solidarities; therefore, this synthesis seeks to interrogate how knowledge is understood, and to open possibilities for thinking and doing otherwise (Lipari 2009).

Contingency and Formation: Henderson's Early Trajectories

Born in 1941, Australian composer Moya Henderson's love for music began in early childhood, yet the first decade of her adult life was spent as a nun of the Sacré Coeur, before severing ties with the church in the 1960s to study composition at the University of Queensland (Macarthur 1988). This biographical trace is offered not as a story of origins, but as one of the many complex contingencies that shaped Henderson's later negotiations with institutions and subsequently, her creative practice. Often described as autodidactic, Henderson arrived at the Hochschule für Musik and Tanz in Köln in 1974, under the primary mentorship of Mauricio Kagel, and peripherally with Karlheinz Stockhausen (Volans 2025). Drawn to the emergent field of Neue Musiktheatre, where irony, parody, and the absurd function as catalysts for creativity and resistance, Henderson quickly achieved notable success, including winning the Kranichstein Prize at the 1974 Darmstadter Ferienkurse für Neue Musik for her composition *Clearing the Air*. In 1976 during Henderson's second year of studies in Cologne, through the trust of her teacher Mauricio Kagel, she embarked on a collaboration that would profoundly shape her creative trajectory: a commission from Düsseldorf based artist Helfried Hagenberg to compose for his sculpture *So-no-re*. This encounter resulted in Henderson's composition *Sekko*, a unique work that was pivotal in initiating Henderson's sustained exploration into instrument design.

Sonic Entanglements: *So-no-re*

Helfried Hagenberg (1940–2022), an artist and professor at the Fachhochschule Düsseldorf, created *So-no-re* in 1974 as a sound sculpture he conceived as part of his broader series of psaligraphic works. Comprising 27 individual triangle-shaped instruments, *So-no-re* was designed to function as a singular, unified sounding instrument. To refine its acoustic properties, Hagenberg collaborated with acoustician Bernd Enders, to extensively analyse the harmonic spectrum of each "triangle" (Figure 1). Each of the 27 objects were suspended individually on fine nylon fishing line, spaced approximately 40 centimetres apart. Visually, the sculpture presents a gradual transition: the front beginning with the shape of a triangle, progressing through nine increasingly square like forms until reaching the shape of a square, then evolving through nine more shapes into a circle, and finally returning through nine further transformations to complete the cycle back at a triangle.

To compose for the sculpture, Henderson developed a unique tablature notation in which the lines and spaces of the staff correspond to an individual triangle, with each triangle receiving a number from 1 to 27. One sonic challenge that Henderson found

was that the lengths of steel of the triangles were all close to the same length, approximately 710mm long with a circular diameter of 10mm each. This resulted in only a range of eight semitones for the entire sculpture. To address this, Henderson collaborated closely with the percussionist Nicholas Bardach of Christoph Caskel's percussion studio, exploring the timbral possibilities of *So-no-re*.

Figure 1: Helfried Hagenberg's *So-no-re* (1974), Münster Gallery exhibit (Image © Helfried Hagenberg, provided by and used with the permission of Monika Hagenberg).

To address the sonic and temporal limitations of *So-no-re*, Henderson undertook a series of experiments using metal, rubber and wooden beaters, fine wire brushes, and even kitchen whisks. She also further explored a repertoire of playing techniques, from dampening with hands and beaters, varying hand and striking pressures, and creating “vibration tones” by applying resonators above and below the objects to amplify their fundamental tones (Henderson 1984, p. 9). Eventually, by attaching plastic “bottle-resonators”, Henderson recalls that she “had managed to stumble onto a unique method of greatly enhancing the otherwise silent sounds of triangles. That was just the start of my journey” (1984, p. 9). This moment underscores how Henderson's innovations emerged through pure curiosity, through embodied experimentation in a domestic setting, rather than through institutional or formal instruction on composition.

***Sekko* and the Theatre of Procedures**

Premiered by Nicholas Bardach at the Hochschule für Musik und Tanz Köln on the 16th of March 1976, Henderson titled her composition, *Sekko: for its water*, a play on words reflecting the conditions of the sounds and their manifestation (Figure 2) (Henderson 2025).

From a critical lens, the premiere can be read as a tension within the institutional apparatus—an event that frames and legitimizes experimental work, offering conditions of visibility and privilege that might otherwise remain inaccessible. Yet, *Sekko* also marks a pivotal historical juncture in Henderson's creative trajectory, underscoring her curiosity of complex acoustic phenomena and instrument design. Each of the 27 objects in *So-no-re* became a site of sonic investigation, generating a catalogue of techniques for

Figure 2: Nicholas Bardach premiering *Sekko* at the Hochschule für Musik and Tanz Köln, Aula, 1976 (Image © Helfried Hagenberg, provided by and used with the permission of Monika Hagenberg).

Sekko and for Henderson moving forward. This process extended beyond conventional compositional or notational practices of the time, exploring objects of banality in the everyday domestic space, highlighting the contingent and embodied nature of Henderson’s approach to composition.

Henderson recalls:

Suspending a triangle on a length of cord just outside my kitchen in Cologne in order to try out an array of kitchen utensils as beaters for the instrument because I was hoping to produce some new and unusual sounds. I had also cut a plastic mineral water bottle in half and, for no apparent reason, held the bottom half against the cord which was supporting the triangle. I struck the triangle and was amazed at what I heard. Unwittingly, and very simply, I’d set up the conditions for the emergence of a quite new sound . . . It was a beautiful sound, and I knew I was onto something.

—Henderson (1984, p. 9)

This anecdote underscores how feminist experiences often manifest outside of conventional compositional frameworks, merging through experimental gestures that demand alternative vocabularies, syntaxes, styles, and forms. Such practices, I argue, can be understood as feminist resistances (Foucault 2003; Mellor 1988). Subsequently, Henderson adopts these “forms of resistance” as her starting point: experimenting with simplistic, unassuming domestic items alongside *So-no-re* to reimagine the ontologies between composer, percussionist, and object (Foucault 2003).

Although limited in its pitch variability, Henderson understood *So-no-re* as Hagenberg intended, as a single dynamic instrument: a theatre of procedures, where the rules of percussion, staging, collaboration, and embodiment were radically reconfigured. Approximately 20 minutes in duration, *Sekko* culminates in a striking visual and sonic gesture: the performer moving in five circular revolutions, in the centre of the triangular frame, arms extended with long wire brushes between the fingers, beginning slowly and accelerating in speed and revolution (Figure 3). This finale is not a mere spectacle,

but the materialization of a conceptual project: a performative gesture of resistance inscribed sonically and spatially on the performers body, the holistic spectral instrument, and the concert space. Bardach later credited this physical approach to performance with teaching him about “stillness as a performer” (Bardach 2025). Such reflection further foregrounds the embodied nature of *Sekko*, where technique is not prescribed or given, but co-constituted through performer-composer negotiations.

Figure 3: Score example from page 21 of Moya Henderson’s *Sekko* (Unpublished score, image © Moya Henderson, used with permission).

Radical Organological Futures

Henderson returned to Australia in late 1976, marking the beginning of a radical engagement with instrument design that unsettled normative paradigms of percussion practice in Australia. Despite the precariousness of freelance life, Henderson declared that, by 1977, she was “irrevocably involved with triangles”, developing what she called resonator-triangles—objects inspired by “Sekko” and Hagenberg’s sculptural aesthetics (Henderson 1984, p. 9). Henderson subsequently designed over three chromatic octaves of resonator-triangles (C3 to F5), an impractical yet visionary set of objects that reimaged the humble triangle as a dynamic sonic assemblage. This work accentuates feminist organology with the potential to imagine new entanglements of corporeality, materiality, and sonic agency.

Henderson’s insistence on the possibility of the triangle persisted throughout the late 1970s and early 1980s, culminating in the invention of the Alemba (Figure 4). Constructed from triangular steel rods with an apex open, each triangle of the Alemba was connected to a quarter-wave tubular resonator via a taut cord and diaphragm, with the instrument encased in a functional wood frame. The instrument was first prototyped and refined during Henderson’s inaugural Australia Council residency in 1983.

By 1985, Henderson had extended the Alemba’s range to include a treble and bass instrument, introducing a tuning system that resonated not only with triangle’s fundamental pitch, but also with its octave and twelfth. Henderson’s radical innovations were trialled with professional contemporary ensembles such as the Percussions de Stras-

Figure 4: Moya Henderson with the Bass and Treble Alemba, 1985 (Image © Moya Henderson, used with permission).

bourg, Synergy Percussion, and the Sydney Symphony Orchestra (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Score example from page 19 of Henderson’s composition *Alanbiq* (1977/1985), originally composed for the Percussions de Strasbourg, later amended for Synergy Percussion (Unpublished score, image © Moya Henderson, used with permission).

Into the 1990s, Henderson further developed the “Tosca Bell”—a pentangle design offering expanded geometric parameters for tuning multiple vibrational modes of the triangle (fundamental, octave, twelfth, minor third). To develop the Tosca Bell, Henderson collaborated with physicists and engineers, conducting empirical tests using finite element modelling (Figure 6). These experiments examined the acoustic potential of the pentangle and soundboard, components meticulously designed to enhance resonance across the instruments range, functioning similarly to a piano or harpsichord soundboard (Fletcher 1984). Such processes foreground Henderson’s curiosity and determination to discover new forms of musicking, rendering visible what Foucault might describe as the conditions of existence (Gutting 2005, p. 48) for feminist approaches to instrument design (2003). Therefore, Henderson’s work challenges normative organologies and opens dialogue for alternative material agencies for keyboard percussion.

Toward a Feminist Organology

Tentatively, through Henderson’s work, I propose the conceptual framework of feminist organology. This is not a taxonomy or a fixed system of classification, but rather a criti-

Figure 6: Chart for measuring frequency spectrum/experiments with Pentangles (Image © Moya Henderson, used with permission).

cal orientation: a “new organology” that interrogates the epistemic, material, relational, and social conditions of instrumentality (Tresch and Dolan 2013). A feminist organology therefore asks: what is being classified, why, how, and under what conditions? It examines instruments as sites of gendered labour and acknowledges the embodied negotiations that shape our relations and doings in practice (Magnusson 2017, p. 291; Tresch and Dolan 2013). Unlike traditional organology—which privileges lineage, progression, and origins—a feminist organology, although speculative, underscores the provisional, reciprocal and contextually embedded nature of musical knowledge, resisting totalizing orthodoxies and the assumption that instruments are neutral objects to be exploited, asking critically: what epistemologies shape and prescribe our musical present?

Subsequently, I argue that Henderson’s work is feminist inquiry, as it exemplifies this conceptual orientation. Her improvisations with the banal, alongside complex sculptural aesthetics, reveal inventions that emerge through embodied encounters rather than transactional, hierarchical, or institutional modes and prescriptions. Therefore, *Sekko* reconfigures the lore and hierarchies underpinning percussion histories, disrupting relations between composer, performer, and instrument, and challenging assumptions embedded in post-instrumental discourse (Stene 2014). Thus, a feminist organology takes such reconfigurations and resistances as starting points for its inquiry: as tools to interrogate the conditions under which musical conventions, and the canons they sustain, are produced and replicated in the present.

Although *Sekko* is posited as the protagonist in this research, Henderson’s later inventions must be read as sustained continuations of feminist resistance: instruments of sonic, tactile, and agential speculation that resist classification. These instruments are not easily defined or categorized, are rarely acknowledged, and do not sit within the canonical repertoires, techniques, or discussions of the art of percussion. Henderson’s trace thus supports feminist organology as a speculative and provocative frame through which to think anew. It imagines instruments as fragmented yet dynamic assemblages, entangled with bodies and histories, and asks of percussionists: who are “we” in the present?

Therefore, I do not claim feminist organology as an established discipline, rather, I offer this research as provocation—a way of imagining what might be possible when reading instruments and histories through feminist genealogies of resistance. What does such a framework enable one to think? With whom can we think alongside? What new conceptual work could emerge through the lens of a feminist organology?

Conclusion: Provocations for Thinking Otherwise

This research, while speculative, traces the feminist genealogies of Moya Henderson’s experiments in percussion and instrument design. In doing so, it offers feminist organology as a way of reimagining percussion instruments as dynamic assemblages, entangled with bodies, and histories, and invites new ways of conceptualising and enacting musical relations. Subsequently, this research asks: what might percussion look like if feminist organology were embraced as a critical orientation? What is the highest dream we could dream (Torrence 2025)?

This work honours Donna Haraway’s call to make trouble—“to settle and rebuild” (Haraway 2016, p. 1)—to foster historical manifestations of kinships and to explore feminist narratives as practices of care and collective thinking, as articulated in the statement that “it matters what stories we tell to tell other stories with; it matters what knots knot knots, what thoughts think thoughts, what descriptions describe descriptions, what ties tie ties” (Lloyd-Jones 2024, p. 35). Therefore, by tracing Moya Henderson’s work and acknowledging *Sekko/So-no-re* as a catalyst for her subsequent instrument designs, this research reveals the potential of feminist organology as a conceptual framework for sustained feminist critique of the structures of power and knowledge in Western art music.

Henderson’s instruments have much more life to be lived, and although they resist definition and categorisation, they can be understood through Henderson’s radical lived experiences, artistic tenets, and the genealogies they generate. Thus, to think through Henderson’s work via feminist organology is to invite dissent, multiplicities, and critical celebration. It invites a critical historiographic reading of percussion’s formation and successions, one that disrupts fixed absolutes of the past, and reframes them as contingent possibilities for sense making in the present.

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